

DIAGNOSIS OF RENAL VASCULAR DISEASES IN PATIENTS WITH ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION BY THE MODERN METHODS

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Relevance: The characteristics of this method, namely its accuracy (92%), sensitivity and specificity (100%) make it possible to use it as the main non-invasive method for diagnosing and monitoring rejection of a transplanted kidney, occlusion of renal graft vessels, make it possible to refuse angiographic examination to confirm the diagnosis. Dopplerography provides unique information about the vascular architectonics and circulatory features of the kidney affected by any pathological process, as well as in the contralateral kidney, which will have to ensure the vital activity of the body in the case of nephroectomy.

The purpose of the study. To assess the condition of renal vessels in patients with arterial hypertension by ultrasound dopplerography.

Material and methods: The work is based on the analysis of the results of the examination of 60 people with arterial hypertension. Of these, in 12 patients, when using combinations of two or three antihypertensive drugs, it was practically impossible to reduce blood pressure to satisfactory values.

The following examination methods were used: examination of complaints, anamnesis and physical examination, laboratory, electrocardiography, ultrasound and Dopplerography, nephroscintigraphy, X-ray.

Results: In 25 patients with hypertension I, II art. and chronic pyelonephritis (hypertension 1-15, HYPERTENSION II-10), the following blood flow indicators were obtained: peak systolic velocity fluctuated at the mouth of the main trunk of the right renal artery from 90.0 cm/s to 95.0 cm/s, with an average value of 93.0 cm/s. In the left renal artery, the peak systolic blood flow rate varied from 85.0 to 93.0 cm/s, with an average value of 90.0 cm/s.

Conclusions: Ultrasound Dopplerography of kidney vessels is necessary for all patients with arterial hypertension. The data of dopplerography of renal vessels in patients with hypertension of 1 st. do not allow to identify statistically significant changes in blood flow parameters in comparison with the control group.

References:

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